

Considerations on Voltage Ripple Assessment in dc Power Network

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Abstract—The main components used for integration in the power system of distributed renewable energy sources, basically work in dc, f.i. batteries, photovoltaic systems and fuel cells. In addition, most common loads already use dc power internally, usually provided by rectifiers. Consequently, the usage of generated energy can be made more effective if directly delivered to load through a dc grid or microgrids, with improvements in efficiency, costs and reliability. The HVDCs are already widely used for their convenience over long-distance bulk power transmission. Despite this wide usage of the dc power network, the Power Quality definition and assessment in dc is still in an unstandardised situation. This paper focuses on a specific PQ phenomenon typical of dc networks: voltage ripple. Observations are made on the sources of this phenomenon and a methodology is proposed for measuring the intensity of this disturbance by introducing synthetic indices, also with reference to the most recent technical standards, with the specific scope to the compatibility level assessment. The proposed measurement techniques are applied to experimental data acquired on the power supply of a dc railway system.

Keywords—dc grid, LVDC, HVDC, Rectifier, Power Converter, Power Quality, Ripple Measurement.

I. INTRODUCTION

The adoption of a large number of distributed generations of Renewable Energy Sources (RESs) into power systems is seen as the only solution to cope with environmental issues, drastically reducing Green House Gas (GHG) emissions. Usually, to mitigate the problem related to the energy balances, the RESs are organised in microgrids with distributed storage systems too. In this configuration, RESs are spreading more and more all over the world. Most microgrids adopt ac distribution as well as conventional power systems. So, dc output type sources, such as photovoltaic (PV) systems, fuel cells, and energy storage systems (e.g., batteries and supercapacitors) need inverters to be linked to the ac distribution network. [1], [2].

But, on the other side, the development in power electronics has raised the number of appliances that operate in dc, so further conversions ac/dc are needed in order to supply them from conventional 50/60 Hz ac distribution systems. All this implies conversion losses that greatly impact the overall energy efficiency. Better integration of distributed energy sources can be achieved with the utilization of dc at the distribution layer. In this way, it is possible a direct connection of dc loads to dc energy sources, removing all losses due to energy conversion systems. So, there is a growing interest in using dc power systems and microgrids for electricity distribution. [3]-[4]. In addition, for many years, High-voltage dc (HVDC) transmission is considered advantageous and, in some cases, superior to ac in applications such as long underwater cable crossing, long distance bulk power

transmission, stable ac interconnection, inerties with low short-circuit levels, coupling 50/60 Hz systems, and long-distance underground cable systems [5].

With this wide diffusion of dc power network, in a similar way to what has already happened for the ac, the topic of Power Quality (PQ) is gaining more and more attention to avoid systems failure or performance degradation [6]-[13]. Voltage quality shall be specified to provide a system engineer with a reference to design the various parts of a plant: supply, distribution, and loads. Voltage quality requirements may be different for different target applications and respective system topologies. The voltage variation, transients, and other voltage disturbances must not exceed the application-specific limits of the operating ranges, nor the values tolerated by the devices involved. Ideally, a dc source is considered perfect when it exhibits a stable voltage within a normal band. Voltage quality should be defined in terms of limits to disturbances intended as deviations outside this band. These deviations outside this band may be stationary and transient. Use case, application and electromagnetic environment-specific compatibility levels shall be defined for temporary voltage variations, voltage dips and swells, flicker, and dc voltage fluctuations, in terms of maximum duration and magnitudes.

Despite the increasing attention to this matter from scientific literature, the PQ standards are mainly oriented towards the ac systems [14]-[17], and, to the best of the authors' knowledge, there are very few standard documents about PQ assessment in dc [18]-[19]. At present, even the international standards addressing PQ issues are focused on ac power networks and cannot be easily applied or extended to the dc systems [13]. To support the transition towards the dc grids and improve the reliability of such systems, it is fundamental to define unified guidelines for a traceable measurement and characterization of PQ in dc. To this aim, this paper focus on a specific PQ phenomenon typical of the dc network: voltage ripple, and the problem of its standardized measurement procedure is discussed with the specific reference to the compatibility level assessment. Few scientific papers try to face a similar topic [7]-[12]. In [12], Ripple indexes based on frequency domain (f.i. Sum of Amplitude and Sum of Amplitude and Phases) are proposed to keep the similarity with ac PQ metrics, while the time-domain indexes, based on peak-to-peak and percentiles, do not need to deal with the lack of fundamental and harmonics. In [7], interruptions, RVC (Rapid Voltage Changes) and ripple are considered, and some related indexes are proposed for their characterization. In both, the measurement procedures are not well described/standardized.

This paper explores this theme, starting from the source of ripple phenomenon. Then, accounting of the most relevant

technical standards and the scientific literature about PQ in ac and dc, a methodology is proposed for measuring the intensity of this disturbance by introducing synthetic indices with the specific scope of the compatibility level assessment. As an example of application, the proposed measurement techniques are applied to experimental data acquired on the power supply of a dc railway system obtaining preliminary results.

II. RIPPLE AND AC/DC CONVERTERS

Ripple in dc power network can be defined as unwanted periodic deviations (or fluctuation) with respect to the average value of supply quantity (voltage or current) [18]. Typically, in steady-state conditions, the voltage ripple is originated by the conversion of ac main energy source in a dc network. To this aim, the passive rectifiers are the most adopted solution and, in this case, the deviation occurs at frequencies that are related to the main ac supply frequency (50/60 Hz typically). Nevertheless, also active rectifiers can be adopted to this scope, and, in this case, the fluctuations can appear also at frequencies not correlated with the main ac frequency, due to the switching frequency and the working condition of the rectifier [20]. For this reason, in the following, the most common configurations of both type of rectifiers are analysed to evaluate the expected ripple level.

Single-phase rectifiers

The half-wave rectifier is the most basic topology, based on a single diode placed at the secondary of the transformer (see Fig.1). In the case of resistive-inductive load, a further diode in parallel to the load itself is present to avoid overvoltages. The load voltage is a half-sinusoid, and the analytical expression of one period of the supplied voltage can be written as:

$$v_L(t) = \begin{cases} nV_p \sin(\omega t) & 0 \leq \omega t < \pi \\ 0 & \pi \leq \omega t < 2\pi \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where V_p and n represent the maximum of the primary voltage and n the transformer ratio respectively. It is evident that the employment of the half-wave rectifier is limited to few applications at very low power, due to its poor performances (see Table I). A more widespread topology is the full-wave rectifier (see Fig. 2), which allows a better rectification process that occurs in both half-cycles of the input ac signal. It follows that the output voltage is a full-wave rectified sine and one period of the obtained waveform is given by:

$$v_L(t) = nV_p \sin(\omega t) \quad (2)$$

with $-\frac{\pi}{2} \leq \omega t \leq +\frac{\pi}{2}$. The reduced period implies a doubled ripple frequency, a higher average load voltage (V_L), and a reduced relative fluctuation $\Delta V/V_L$, see Table I.

Three-phase rectifiers

Three-phase rectifiers are mainly employed for high power applications, such as traction systems. They can be combined to achieve a higher number of pulses, and so a lower ripple amplitude. The most widespread solution to convert the three-phase power in dc is the six-pulse bridge rectifier shown in Fig. 3. As for the single-phase full-bridge configuration, the conducting diode pair is the one with the higher voltage drop. This implies that the load voltage has six pulses and each diode has a conduction interval of $2/3\pi$ therefore, it can be expressed as:

Fig. 1. Half-wave rectifier (resistive load)

Fig. 2. Full-wave bridge rectifier

Fig. 3. Six-pulse rectifier

$$v_L(t) = \sqrt{3}nV_p \cos(\omega t - \pi/3) \quad (3)$$

where $-\frac{\pi}{6} \leq \omega t \leq +\frac{\pi}{6}$ and V_p represents the phase voltage. This implies that ripple frequency becomes six times the fundamental system ac frequency. It can be worth noting that the presence of 6 pulses in the period allows having a quite low ripple amplitude ($\Delta V/V_L = 14.03\%$).

A rectifier with 12 pulses can be easily realized by combining in series or parallel two six-pulses rectifiers [20]. The two bridges are connected at the secondary as delta and as star respectively to obtain a phase displacement of $\pi/6$ radians. The transformer ratios are chosen differently to compensate for the difference among line and line to line voltages. This implies the same secondary peaks so that the output voltage is equal to:

$$v_L(t) = \sqrt{3}nV_p \cos(\omega t - 12)\cos(\pi/12) \quad (4)$$

where $-\frac{\pi}{2} \leq \omega t \leq +\frac{\pi}{2}$. In other words, the behaviour of $v_L(t)$ is quite similar to the previous case, but the time interval between two consecutive peaks is halved from which follows that the ripple amplitude is lower ($\Delta V/V_L = 3.445\%$). Rectifiers with a number of pulses greater than 12 are not often used given that the potential advantages in terms of ripple amplitude and harmonics are limited and partially compensated by their growing complexity.

Table I summarizes the main characteristics of the rectifiers above described in the simplified considered working conditions. It is worthwhile noting that increasing the number of pulses, the ripple amplitude decreases, and the frequency of its fundamental component increases. In fact, the frequency of the ripple is k times the input voltage frequency, where k represents the number of pulses. This allows reduced costs and an easier design of the output filtering stage.

TABLE I. RECTIFIERS MAIN CHARACTERISTICS

Type	Output voltage	V_L	$\Delta V/V_L$	Frequency
Half-wave		$(\pi/\pi) \cdot V_p$	314.1 %	f
Full-wave		$(2\pi/\pi) \cdot V_p$	157.1 %	$2f$
Six-pulse		$(3\pi/\pi) \cdot V_p$	14.03 %	$6f$
Twelve-pulse		$(6\pi/\pi) \cdot V_p$	3.445 %	$12f$
PWM rectifier		$>nV_p$	$< 1\%$	f_s

The converters considered so far are passive and the output level can be regulated only statically by choosing transformer ratio (n), moreover, they absorb non-sinusoidal currents. Introducing active switches with various control strategies (see Fig. 4), it is possible to absorb with unitary power factor from the ac side and to regulate the output dc voltage level dynamically. Active rectifiers allow bidirectional power flow, enabling the possibility to inject power in the ac side in case of an active distribution network (i.e. in presence of RES). For three-phase Pulse Width Modulated (PWM) rectifiers, the output dc voltage $v_L(t)$ fluctuates around its average value V_L , with a peak-to-peak excursion that depends on the filter capacitance C_d and can be approximately computed as:

$$\Delta V = \frac{V_S \cdot I_S}{\omega \cdot C_d V_L} \quad (5)$$

where V_S and I_S are voltage and current amplitude at the secondary respectively. The ripple ΔV is generally few percentages of V_L [20].

The ripple amplitudes of Table I are theoretical values and apply only in ideal main supply conditions (symmetrical three-phase pure sinusoidal voltage). In particular, the presence of harmonics changes the shape of ripple and introduces higher frequency components. While the presence of interharmonics or, in three phase configurations, asymmetries in terms of amplitude or phase can alter the ripple periodicity introducing lower order frequency components.

The situation becomes more complex for controlled rectifiers: the characteristics of voltage ripple, in terms of amplitude and shape, depend on the dc voltage and current levels, dc circuit reactance, converter topology, converter switching frequency, and converter control strategies, whereas, in non-ideal conditions, they can be influenced also by feedback measurement errors and/or control errors,

Fig. 4. PWM rectifier

asymmetry between impedances and harmonics, interharmonics and unbalance in the ac supply. Resonance conditions within the dc system resulting in potential amplifications have to be considered. Some resonance phenomena will be shown in the following.

Finally, it is worthwhile to recall that, in some systems, a filtering stage is collocated after the rectifier. Broadly speaking, its effect is a remarkable reduction of the ripple and so a more stable dc voltage is found in the supplied network.

III. RIPPLE ASSESSMENT

There is a wide interest in the conducted disturbances in dc power systems, not only ripple but also voltage dips or swells, voltage fluctuations, etc. Nevertheless, as mentioned before, there is a lack of international standards that univocally define PQ indexes, measuring procedures, and the corresponding compatibility and immunity thresholds, with specific reference to the dc system. The TR-63282 [18] represents a first normative effort in this field. It provides some recommendations for the standardization of voltage levels and related aspects (PQ, EMC, and measurement ...) for dc systems up to 1500 V (Low Voltage dc systems - LVDC) but it is far from completely covering the subject.

It is worthwhile to analyse the main differences that characterize the study of PQ applied to the dc with respect to the most diffused ac PQ. First of all, in dc systems, there is no fundamental frequency and the concept of harmonic distortion, largely used for ac PQ, does not apply, consequently, the common definitions of power quality, typically involving harmonic and interharmonic distortion limits in ac systems, are not applicable. At the same time, as shown in the previous section, spectral components of the ripple can be at ac fundamental frequency or its harmonics. But adopting active rectifiers some other spectral components can be present on the generated voltage. In ac, the basic measurement bandwidth required for the harmonics of mains, is recommended up to 2 kHz, but, in compliance with the latest IEC standards, this range should be extended up to 150 kHz to include the effects of modern fast switching devices [17]. The dc spectral analysis could start with the same basic bandwidth and, if necessary, follow an analogue extension.

In addition, at the delivery point, supplied loads can influence the ripple levels and shape. In fact, the absorption or the injection of current at frequency different from dc, through the network impedance, produces an additional voltage ripple component that combines in phase with the one eventually already present in the supply voltage at the same frequency. This can result in an increase of the voltage ripple level. For this reason, current emission limits should be foreseen for individual loads or customers to bound their impact on the supply voltage. Furthermore, the dc system operator shall provide information on system impedance also to evaluate

potential resonances. So, a new load before connection at a certain point of a dc system, should be subjected to compatibility assessment: starting from the pre-existing ripple, the distortion of load current should be analysed to evaluate its impact on the voltage ripple taking into consideration the network impedance. So, the connection of a new user should not result in levels of distortion or fluctuation of the existing dc system voltage, exceeding a certain threshold.

Measurement procedure

The TR-63282 [18] suggests that a comparison of average dc and ac RMS values might be the basis for setting power quality indexes for LVDC systems. Focusing on ripple measurement, defining dc value (or mean value) as:

$$U_{dc} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} u_i, \quad \text{with } \frac{n}{f_s} = t_a \quad (6)$$

where u_i are samples of the waveform and n is the number of samples, f_s is the sampling frequency and t_a is the analysis time; defining RMS value in time (7) or frequency (8) domain as:

$$U_{rms} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} u_i^2} \quad (7)$$

$$U_{rms} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^m U_i^2} \quad (8)$$

where U_i is the RMS value of the i -th spectral component, the technical report proposes the definitions of the dc ripple in RMS as:

$$U_{rpl} = \sqrt{U_{rms}^2 - U_{DC}^2} \quad \text{or} \quad U_{rpl} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m U_i^2} \quad (9)$$

and of the relative dc ripple (%) as:

$$u_{rpl} = \frac{\sqrt{U_{rms}^2 - U_{DC}^2}}{U_{DC}} \cdot 100 \quad \text{or} \quad u_{rpl} = \frac{U_{rpl}}{U_{DC}} \cdot 100 \quad (10)$$

A future standard should, first of all, take a clear position between the time or frequency domain approach, in order to unequivocally define common guidelines for a measurement method. In the following the authors, adopt a time domain approach.

Flagging Concept

Despite the definitions (9) and (10) appear quite clear, there are some important aspects that should be considered for their practical application. To this aim reference could be made to the IEC 61000 family standards [16],[17],[19], analysing the main aspects of PQ measuring procedures, that are already introduced by ac PQ standards and extending them to ripple dc assessment. The standard [17] clearly states that the measurement methods, used for the characterization of quasi-stationary signals, are not applicable or lead to unreliable results when non-stationary disturbances occur (i.e. it is not possible to measure harmonics when voltage dips, swells or interruptions occur). For this reason, the [17] introduces the flagging concept: when the measurement algorithm detects a dip, swell or interruption, the data related to the time interval in which the event takes place are "flagged" and also the indexes, obtained with reference to stationary PQ phenomena. These results are not considered in standard statistical analysis and are used only for specific purposes. The flagging avoids

multiple counting of a single event in different parameters (for example, counting a single voltage dip both as a dip and a transient oscillation). If during a given time interval any value is flagged, the aggregated value (i.e. at 3 s or 10 min) which includes that value, shall also be flagged, to indicate that it might be unreliable. It can be reasonable to use the same flagging concept also for ripple assessment.

Several flagging techniques can be adopted, for example, the maximum and minimum value of samples can be compared with two thresholds, otherwise, it is possible to perform a statistical analysis and identify the outliers (> 3 or 4 times the standard deviation), etc. [21], [22].

The flagging technique, adopted in the following, estimates the first derivative of the voltage waveform and compares it with a threshold as expressed in (11):

$$\frac{du(t)}{dt} > \frac{U_{DC}}{2} \text{ V/s} \quad (11)$$

Inside the measurement time interval (200 ms), if the first derivative is greater than 50% of U_{dc} the interval is flagged. The 1st derivative has been approximated by the ratio between forward difference and sampling time. A moving average (over 20 ms) has been introduced, to reduce the noise.

IV. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

In this section, some experimental results, coming from a measurement campaign conducted in a railway dc conversion substation, are presented. It is located next to Forli and is part of the Italian railway system. The rated voltage of the monitored track is 3 kV dc. The supply system is a twelve-pulse rectifier equipped with a filtering inductance. Proper resistive-capacitive compensated voltage dividers have been adopted to acquire line voltages before and after the filtering stage. A commercially available measurement system has been employed, with a sampling frequency of 50 kHz, and 24 bit of amplitude resolution. The measurement campaign lasted about 2 months with about 1 TB of recorded data.

In Fig. 5, an example of the waveform acquired at the output of the rectifier, before the filtering stage, is shown. The 12 pulses of the hexa-phase rectifier can be clearly distinguished. In Fig. 6, the voltage acquired at the output of

Fig. 5. Rectified voltage before the filtering stage

Fig. 6. Rectified voltage after the filtering stage

the filter in the same time interval is shown. The filtering impact is evident: the peak-to-peak voltage reduces considerably from almost 320 V to 36 V. This corresponds to a relative dc ripple, calculated as (10), that decreases from 2.5 % to 0.2 %. As it can be seen, Fig. 5 does not show the typical behaviour of a 12-pulse rectifier previously seen in Table 1. In fact, theoretically, the peak-to-peak voltage (ΔV) should not exceed 120 V. This is probably due to a voltage unbalance at the input ac side.

Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 show two examples of transient events recorded during the measurement campaign. These time intervals have been detected by the above-described flagging algorithm (11). The first is a fast voltage transient, probably due to the insertion of some auxiliary loads (minor loads inside trains). The second is an oscillatory transient in which probably a resonance phenomenon occurs, in fact, the oscillation frequency is 120 Hz, thus it is not due to the rectifier. Line reactance together with substation and train filters could cause damped oscillation of voltage in correspondence of a step increment in current due to the insertion of a load. As stated before, the resonance could amplify the PQ phenomena.

Ripple assessment has been performed over 24 hours of data recorded during the measurement campaign. The acquired samples have been split into time intervals of 200 ms in agreement with [17]; the aforementioned flagging algorithm (11) is used to exclude intervals in which other power quality events occur. The dc ripple in RMS has been evaluated with (9). In Fig. 9 the Probability Density Function (PDF) and Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of measured values are shown. As it can be seen, the average ripple is 9.7 V rms, but the distribution is bimodal. This indicates that most of the occurrences are between 7.6 V and 9.7 V, but there is a non-neglecting probability of having 17.5 V of RMS ripple.

Fig. 7. Example of event to flag: fast voltage transient.

Fig. 8. Example of event to flag: oscillatory transient

During the analysed day, 151 PQ events have been detected by the flagging algorithm, and the corresponding time intervals have been excluded from ripple assessment. In order to highlight the importance of flagging, Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 show the PDFs of ripples computed respectively on the 151 flagged intervals and on 151 non-flagged immediately successive time intervals.

As expected, the ripple computed on flagged intervals is not correct and is an overestimation of the actual ripple. In fact, the mean value is over 15 V rms. Instead, the average drops to 11 V if calculated immediately after the flagged time windows.

Fig. 9. Statistical analysis of RMS ripple on 24 hours.

Fig. 10. PDF and CDF of RMS ripple computed on the 151 flagged intervals.

Fig. 11. PDF and CDF of RMS ripple, on immediately successive intervals.

The unbalanced in three-phase supply voltage, asymmetries in grid or rectifier, as stated in section II, implies the presence of unexpected spectral components at frequencies lower than 12 times the ac fundamental frequency. Note that this can happen also if the input transformer is not perfectly symmetric on the six phases. To take into account all these asymmetries, in place of a single value of the turn ratio n in (4), six equivalent ratios n_1, \dots, n_6 , one for each phase, can be considered. The presence of asymmetries is confirmed by the spectrum shown in Fig.12. In fact, besides the 600 Hz component, two spectral components, respectively at 300 Hz and 100 Hz are present. Note that those low frequency spectral components are not removed by filtering, as it is designed not to account for them, in fact, they persist also after the filter (Fig.13).

CONCLUSIONS

The dc power networks are experiencing great development without the existence of specific standards that define procedures for the power quality measurements. This paper faces this issue with specific reference to the voltage ripple measurement, which is a PQ phenomenon typical of dc networks. The technical report [18] proposes a voltage ripple indicator, without paying attention to aggregation time intervals and flagging procedure. The authors propose an extension of this index, suggesting a measurement procedure based on a flagging algorithm conceived for dc. The procedure has been applied to experimental data acquired in a dc substation. Examples of transient events, in which the flagging is needed, have been shown, together with the effect of asymmetries on the output ripple. Finally, a static analysis highlights the importance of flagging.

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Fig. 12. Spectrum of the rectified voltage before the filtering stage

Fig. 13. Spectrum of the rectified voltage after the filtering stage

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